

**THE IMPACT OF TRAINING AND MANPOWER DEVELOPMENT
ON PRODUCTIVITY IN PUBLIC ORGANISATIONS
(A STUDY OF NASARAWA STATE FIRE SERVICE 2015–2020)**

Esther Kingsley Edeh

Department of Public Administration Veritas University Abuja, Nigeria

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Keywords:

*Training,
Manpower
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Abstract: *This study investigates the impact of training and manpower development on productivity in public organisations, with a specific focus on the Nasarawa State Fire Service (2015–2020). Adopting a descriptive survey research design, data were collected from 60 respondents selected from a population of 71 employees using Taro Yamane’s formula. Structured questionnaires and semi-structured interviews served as the primary instruments for data collection. Quantitative data were analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 28, employing descriptive and inferential statistics, while qualitative data were thematically analysed to provide contextual insights. Findings revealed that training significantly enhances employee productivity, efficiency, and emergency response capacity. Manpower development was shown to improve organisational performance by fostering teamwork, discipline, and service delivery. Long-term benefits of training included raised morale and enthusiasm, reduction of workplace hazards, and sustained quality of service. However, persistent challenges such as poor funding, inadequate manpower, and lack of training facilities were identified as critical barriers undermining effective manpower development. Results further confirmed a strong positive relationship between structured training, manpower development, and organisational productivity in the Fire Service. The study recommends increased government funding, institutionalisation of structured training policies, provision of modern training facilities, recruitment of additional staff, and partnerships with local and international fire academies. It also advocates the integration of digital training tools such as e-learning and simulation-based platforms to complement traditional methods. By situating manpower development within the operational realities of Nigeria’s public sector emergency services, the study contributes practical insights for*

Esther Kingsley Edeh

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policymakers, administrators, and scholars seeking to enhance institutional capacity, staff productivity, and public service effectiveness.

1. Introduction

Training and manpower development are widely acknowledged as critical drivers of organisational effectiveness and employee productivity. They equip staff with the knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary to meet evolving workplace demands and achieve strategic goals (Adeniji, 2015; Cole, 1997). In public sector organisations, where service delivery often depends on timely response and operational efficiency, systematic training enhances performance, reduces occupational hazards, and strengthens institutional capacity (Olaniyan & Ojo, 2008). Globally, human capital theory underscores training as an investment that yields long-term gains in productivity, efficiency, and employee morale (Becker, 1975; Armstrong, 2006). Effective manpower development programmes ensure that employees remain adaptable to technological, environmental, and administrative changes while improving organisational resilience in the face of uncertainty (Nassazi, 2013). In Nigeria, however, public institutions frequently grapple with inadequate training infrastructure, limited funding, and poor implementation of development programmes, thereby weakening their ability to perform optimally (Adele & Ibietan, 2017).

The Nasarawa State Fire Service (NSFS), established to provide emergency response and fire prevention services, represents a critical arm of public safety in the state. Given the hazardous nature of firefighting, personnel require continuous capacity building, exposure to modern safety practices, and specialised training. Yet, the NSFS has historically faced challenges in maintaining adequate manpower and accessing standardised training facilities, thereby hindering its capacity to safeguard lives and property effectively.

Problem Statement

Despite the recognised importance of manpower training and development in enhancing organisational performance, many Nigerian public institutions continue to struggle with poor training implementation, insufficient funding, and inadequate facilities (Nwachukwu, 2006; Okotoni & Erero, 2005). In the Nasarawa State Fire Service, these challenges manifest in the form of limited professional development opportunities, lack of structured training policies, and reliance on ad hoc capacity-building initiatives. Such weaknesses undermine employee productivity, reduce morale, and compromise the Service's ability to respond effectively to fire outbreaks and emergencies.

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Previous studies have consistently identified poor funding, political interference, and inadequate facilities as barriers to effective manpower training in Nigeria's public sector (Eneanya, 2009; Ewuim & Ubochi, 2007). However, empirical evidence specific to the fire service sector remains sparse. This creates a knowledge gap in understanding how training and manpower development directly influence productivity, organisational performance, and occupational safety within state-level emergency services. Addressing this gap is essential for strengthening institutional capacity, ensuring public safety, and enhancing the long-term effectiveness of the Nasarawa State Fire Service.

Objectives of the Study

General Objective: To examine the impact of training and manpower development on productivity in the Nasarawa State Fire Service.

Specific Objectives:

1. To determine whether training enhances employee productivity in the Fire Service.
2. To examine the extent to which manpower development contributes to organisational performance.
3. To identify the long-term effects of training on employee productivity and service delivery.
4. To assess the challenges confronting manpower training and development in the Nasarawa State Fire Service.

5. To recommend measures for strengthening training and manpower development in public sector emergency services.

Research Questions

1. What is the impact of training on employee productivity in the Fire Service?
2. How does manpower development contribute to improving organisational performance?
3. What are the long-term effects of training on employee productivity and service delivery?
4. What challenges hinder effective manpower training and development in the Fire Service?
5. What strategies can improve training and manpower development in the Nasarawa State Fire Service?

Significance of the Study

This study is significant because it bridges the gap between human capital development theory and the practical realities of manpower management in Nigeria's public sector. By situating training and manpower development within the operational context of a state-level emergency service, it provides insights that are both locally relevant and globally comparable.

For practitioners, the findings will highlight actionable strategies for improving staff productivity, operational efficiency, and workplace safety. Specifically, the study demonstrates how systematic training and continuous manpower development can reduce

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workplace hazards, enhance employee morale, and improve the overall effectiveness of emergency response services. This will serve as a practical guide for administrators, human resource managers, and public safety officers in adopting more structured approaches rather than relying solely on ad hoc or experience-based methods.

For policymakers and government agencies, the research underscores the urgent need for institutionalized training frameworks, adequate funding, and standardised capacity-building programmes. It also emphasizes the importance of addressing systemic challenges such as poor infrastructure, inadequate facilities, and limited manpower, which weaken the efficiency of public service organisations. Recommendations from this study can therefore inform evidence-based policy reforms, contributing to stronger institutional capacity and improved public service delivery.

From an academic perspective, the study contributes to the body of knowledge on manpower development and organisational productivity by providing empirical evidence from the fire service sector a domain that has received relatively little scholarly attention in Nigeria. By documenting the relationship between training, manpower development, and productivity, the study enriches comparative research on human resource management in developing economies and offers a basis for

further studies on context-specific challenges and solutions.

2. Literature Review

Conceptual Clarifications

Training is generally defined as a systematic process through which employees acquire the knowledge, skills, and abilities required to perform their current tasks effectively and to adapt to new responsibilities (Tharenou, Saks, & Moore, 2007). It involves structured activities such as workshops, on-the-job coaching, and formal instruction that are designed to improve competence and enhance job performance. Manpower development, on the other hand, extends beyond immediate skill acquisition; it emphasizes long-term professional growth and the preparation of staff for future roles and higher responsibilities (Okoh, 1998). Together, training and manpower development serve as critical mechanisms for improving employee productivity, ensuring organisational sustainability, and enhancing overall service delivery in both public and private institutions (Olaniyan & Ojo, 2008).

In the context of public organisations such as the Nasarawa State Fire Service, training is particularly vital given the hazardous nature of firefighting and emergency response. Regular training enhances the ability of personnel to operate under pressure, adopt new technologies, and maintain safety standards, while manpower development ensures that the organisation

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retains a competent workforce capable of meeting future challenges. Without structured programmes in these areas, public institutions often struggle with inefficiency, low morale, and poor performance.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Human Capital Theory, initially developed by Schultz (1961) and further advanced by Becker (1975). The theory posits that investments in people through education, training, and skill development enhance their productivity and, by extension, contribute to organisational and national growth. Training is conceptualized as an investment rather than a cost, yielding long-term benefits such as improved performance, reduced turnover, and higher adaptability to changing environments (Olaniyan & Okemakinde, 2008).

Within this framework, manpower development is viewed as a strategic tool for sustaining organisational competitiveness, particularly in environments marked by rapid technological and administrative changes. For the fire service sector, Human Capital Theory highlights the importance of equipping personnel with both technical and managerial skills to improve their response capabilities and reduce occupational hazards. Thus, the theory provides a strong rationale for examining the link between training, manpower development, and organisational productivity in public safety institutions.

Empirical Review

Global Perspectives on Training and Manpower Development

International studies consistently affirm that structured training contributes to improved employee productivity and organisational effectiveness. In the UK, Cole (1997) emphasized that employee development programmes lead to increased job satisfaction and organisational commitment. Similarly, Nassazi (2013), studying Ugandan organisations, found that effective training reduced workplace errors, boosted morale, and enhanced overall service delivery. Studies in advanced economies also show that organisations that prioritise continuous manpower development are better positioned to adapt to market and environmental uncertainties (Armstrong, 2006).

Nigerian Perspectives on Training and Manpower Development

In Nigeria, research highlights persistent challenges in implementing training programmes, particularly in public organisations. Nwachukwu (2006) observed that inadequate and irregular training contributes significantly to low productivity in government institutions. Ewuim and Ubochi (2007) further argued that training in Nigeria is often approached in an ad hoc manner, lacking structured frameworks that align with organisational goals. Adele and Ibieta (2017) confirmed that public organisations frequently underfund training, perceiving it as a cost rather than an investment. However, studies

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also show that where structured manpower development is institutionalized, there are measurable improvements in service delivery, employee morale, and organisational efficiency (Obisi, 2011).

Sector-Specific Insights

Within emergency services such as fire and disaster management, training is critical not only for improving productivity but also for ensuring safety and reducing occupational hazards. Studies in Ghana's fire service sector revealed that targeted manpower development programmes reduced accident rates and enhanced operational response times (Shuibin, Benjamin, & Naam, 2020). Similarly, evidence from Nigerian security and paramilitary agencies suggests that ongoing training is essential for maintaining discipline, professionalism, and resilience under hazardous conditions (Emeti, 2015).

Identified Gaps Addressed by this Study

Although existing literature affirms the significance of training and manpower development, there is limited empirical evidence focusing specifically on state-level fire services in Nigeria. Much of the Nigerian research has concentrated on broader public sector organisations or corporate institutions, neglecting the unique demands of emergency response services such as firefighting. Furthermore, while global studies have begun to explore innovative training approaches, such as e-learning and simulation-based methods, these

remain underexplored in the Nigerian context (Mathis & Jackson, 2004).

This study addresses these gaps by situating training and manpower development within the operational realities of the Nasarawa State Fire Service. It provides empirical insights into how structured training influences productivity, safety, and morale in a high-risk public organisation, thereby contributing to both academic discourse and practical policymaking.

3. Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which is appropriate for examining existing practices, perceptions, and relationships in natural organisational settings without manipulating variables (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The descriptive survey design enabled the researcher to systematically capture the views of employees on the role of training and manpower development in enhancing productivity. This approach has been widely applied in public administration and human resource management research, as it allows for both quantitative and qualitative data collection, thereby providing a holistic understanding of the subject matter (Bryman, 2016).

Study Area (Nasarawa State Fire Service)

The study was conducted at the Nasarawa State Fire Service (NSFS), Lafia Headquarters, located in Nasarawa State, North-Central Nigeria. Established to provide fire prevention,

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firefighting, and emergency response services, the NSFS plays a critical role in safeguarding lives and property. The Service operates within a challenging environment marked by inadequate manpower, limited resources, and exposure to occupational hazards. These contextual realities make the Fire Service a relevant institution for assessing how structured training and manpower development can improve employee productivity and organisational performance.

Population and Sample

The target population comprised 71 employees of the Nasarawa State Fire Service, Lafia Headquarters. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's formula, at a 5% margin of error, which yielded a total of 60 respondents. This sample provided a representative proportion of the workforce while maintaining statistical reliability. By focusing on the entire personnel cadre from junior staff to senior officers the study ensured that perspectives across different job roles and responsibilities were adequately captured.

Sampling Techniques

A **simple random sampling technique** was used to select the 60 respondents from the workforce. This method minimized bias and ensured equal representation of all categories of staff in the study. In addition, purposive sampling was employed for the interview component, targeting senior officers and supervisors with extensive knowledge of training programmes and

manpower development challenges within the Service. This mixed sampling approach allowed the study to capture both broad employee perspectives and in-depth managerial insights (Etikan & Bala, 2017).

Data Collection Instruments

Two main instruments were used for data collection:

1. **Structured Questionnaire** – The questionnaire consisted of closed-ended items designed to measure the effectiveness, frequency, and challenges of training and manpower development in the Service. Questionnaires are suitable for obtaining quantifiable data from large groups of respondents (Kothari, 2014).
2. **Interview Guide** – Semi-structured interviews were conducted with selected senior officers to gather qualitative insights on organisational challenges and strategies related to manpower development. This instrument helped capture context-specific issues not easily addressed through questionnaires.

Validity and Reliability of Instruments

To ensure content validity, the instruments were reviewed by two academic experts in public administration and one industry practitioner in human resource development to confirm clarity, relevance, and alignment with the study objectives. A pilot test was conducted with 10 respondents, and necessary modifications were made to improve the clarity of questions. Validity checks through expert review and piloting are

Esther Kingsley Edeh

recognized as essential in survey research (Taherdoost, 2016).

Reliability was tested using Cronbach's alpha, with the questionnaire yielding a coefficient of 0.81, which indicates strong internal consistency and reliability (George & Mallery, 2019).

Methods of Data Analysis

Quantitative data from the questionnaires were coded and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 28. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means) were employed to summarise

respondents' demographic characteristics and perceptions, while inferential statistics (correlation and regression analysis) were applied to test the assumptions and establish the relationship between training, manpower development, and productivity.

For the qualitative data, interview responses were transcribed and analyzed using thematic analysis, which involves identifying, analyzing, and reporting recurring patterns in the data (Braun & Clarke, 2021). The integration of quantitative and qualitative approaches ensured methodological triangulation, thereby strengthening the validity and reliability of the study findings.

4. Results

Descriptive Statistics (Demographics of Respondents)

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (N = 60)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	48	80
	Female	12	20
Age Group	20–30 years	27	45
	31–40 years	23	38
	41–50 years	10	17
Educational Qualification	WASC/GRADE II	33	55
	NCE/OND	18	30
	HND/B.Sc	9	15
Marital Status	Single	18	30
	Married	42	70
Years of Service	0–6 years	3	5
	7–12 years	27	45
	12 years and above	30	50

Source: Field Survey, 2020.

Out of the 60 respondents, 80% were male and 20% female, indicating that the Fire Service is male-dominated due to the hazardous and physically demanding nature of firefighting. The majority of respondents were young and active, with 83% between 20–40 years, reflecting a vibrant workforce. In terms of education, 55% had

WASC/GRADE II qualifications, while only 15% held HND/B.Sc degrees, suggesting limited higher-level professional training among staff. Most respondents (70%) were married, and half (50%) had served for more than 12 years, showing a workforce with significant experience and long service commitment.

Impact of Training on Employee Productivity

Table 2. Effect of Training on Employee Productivity

Rank	Indicator	% of Respondents Reporting	Key Notes
1	Training improves employee productivity	80%	Enhances staff efficiency and task performance
2	Training increases task efficiency	78%	Improves speed and accuracy in work execution
3	Training enhances response in emergencies	82%	Strengthens firefighting and emergency handling skills

Source: Field Survey, 2020.

Analysis of survey responses revealed that training significantly improves productivity in the Fire Service. Specifically:

1. Training improves employee productivity (80%), enabling staff to work more effectively.
2. Training increases task efficiency (78%), ensuring faster and more accurate execution of duties.

3. Training enhances emergency response (82%), equipping firefighters with vital skills to handle hazards.

These findings confirm that structured training is central to boosting employee performance and productivity.

Contribution of Manpower Development to Organisational Performance

Table 3. Extent of Manpower Development in Organisational Performance

Rank	Indicator	% of Respondents Reporting	Key Notes
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1	Manpower development improves organisational performance	75%	Enhances overall effectiveness of the Service
2	Manpower development improves teamwork	79%	Fosters collaboration and collective responsibility
3	Manpower development increases service efficiency	83%	Leads to faster and more reliable service delivery

Source: Field Survey, 2020.

Analysis of responses indicated that manpower development contributes substantially to organisational performance. Results showed that:

1. 75% agreed manpower development enhances overall effectiveness of the Service.
2. 79% stated it improves teamwork, encouraging collaboration.

3. 83% reported it increases service efficiency, leading to quicker and more reliable emergency responses.

This demonstrates that manpower development is crucial for strengthening institutional capacity and operational success.

Long-Term Effects of Training on Productivity and Service Delivery

Table 4. Long-Term Benefits of Training on Productivity

Rank	Indicator	% of Respondents Reporting	Key Notes
1	Training raises morale and enthusiasm	93%	Boosts motivation and job satisfaction
2	Training reduces workplace hazards	86%	Promotes safety and reduces risks
3	Training enhances long-term service delivery	81%	Sustains efficiency and service quality

Source: Field Survey, 2020.

Analysis revealed the following long-term effects of training:

1. 93% agreed it raises morale and enthusiasm, improving motivation.
2. 86% stated it reduces workplace hazards, promoting safety.

3. 81% confirmed it enhances long-term service delivery, sustaining quality outcomes.

These findings show that training produces lasting improvements, ensuring both employee well-being and organisational sustainability.

Challenges Confronting Training and Manpower Development

Table 5. Major Challenges Affecting Training and Development in the Fire Service

Rank	Challenge	% of Respondents Reporting	Key Notes
1	Poor funding	47%	Insufficient budgetary allocation for training
2	Inadequate manpower	37%	Staff shortages limit participation in training
3	Lack of training facilities	16%	Outdated or unavailable infrastructure

Source: Field Survey, 2020.

Analysis of challenges revealed that:

1. Poor funding (47%) was the most critical obstacle, restricting access to modern training.
2. Inadequate manpower (37%) reduced staff participation in training programmes.

3. Lack of facilities (16%) hindered practical skill development.

Together, these factors weaken the Fire Service’s capacity to sustain effective training and manpower development.

Recommended Measures for Strengthening Training and Manpower Development

Table 6. Suggested Strategies for Improving Training and Development

Rank	Recommendation	% of Respondents Supporting	Key Notes
1	Increase government funding	85%	Provides resources for regular training and modern equipment
2	Institutionalise structured training policies	81%	Ensures consistency and standardisation of training
3	Recruit additional manpower	78%	Reduces workload and enables more training opportunities

Esther Kingsley Edeh

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4	Provide modern training facilities	73%	Improves practical learning and skills acquisition
5	Partner with fire academies/institutes	69%	Exposes staff to global best practices

Source: Field Survey, 2020.

Analysis of recommendations showed that respondents emphasized five critical measures:

1. Increased government funding (85%) for sustainable training.
2. Institutionalised training policies (81%) to ensure consistency.
3. Recruitment of additional manpower (78%) to reduce workload pressures.
4. Provision of modern training facilities (73%) to enhance skill acquisition.
5. Partnerships with training institutes (69%) to promote global best practices.

These recommendations, if implemented, would strengthen manpower development and improve emergency service delivery.

5. Discussion

The findings of this study confirm that training and manpower development play a critical role in enhancing employee productivity and organisational performance in the Nasarawa State Fire Service. The identification of training as a driver of efficiency, improved morale, hazard reduction, and long-term service delivery aligns with global literature, which consistently highlights human capital investment as a determinant of organisational success

(Armstrong, 2006; Nassazi, 2013). This reinforces the assertion that public sector institutions, particularly emergency services, are highly dependent on well-trained and motivated personnel to achieve their objectives.

The implications of these findings are far-reaching, affecting all core indicators of organisational effectiveness—productivity, safety, service quality, and staff motivation. For instance, structured training directly enhances employee output and emergency response efficiency, while manpower development strengthens teamwork and overall service delivery. In addition, the long-term benefits, such as raised morale and hazard reduction, ensure sustained improvements in organisational capacity. These outcomes validate Human Capital Theory, which argues that systematic investment in people yields measurable returns in productivity and institutional growth (Becker, 1975).

The study also revealed persistent challenges, including poor funding, inadequate manpower, and lack of training facilities. These constraints are consistent with previous Nigerian studies, which identified financial limitations and weak infrastructure as major barriers to effective manpower development in the public sector

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(Ewuim & Ubochi, 2007; Adele & Ibietan, 2017).

The dominance of funding-related challenges underscores the structural weaknesses in Nigeria's public institutions, where training is often underfunded and irregular. Comparatively, studies in other African and global contexts show that well-funded and institutionalised training frameworks contribute significantly to public service efficiency and resilience (Shuibin, Benjamin & Naam, 2020). This contrast highlights the systemic gaps that continue to hinder the Fire Service from achieving its full potential.

Another important insight from the study is the overwhelming support for reforms to strengthen manpower development. Respondents emphasized the need for increased government funding, structured training policies, provision of modern facilities, recruitment of additional staff, and partnerships with local and international fire academies. These recommendations mirror best practices globally, where continuous training, standardised frameworks, and technological innovations are central to emergency service management (Mathis & Jackson, 2004; Armstrong, 2006). However, the relatively low adoption of modern training technologies in the Fire Service points to a technological gap similar to that observed in other Nigerian public organisations.

In sum, this discussion underscores the fact that effective training and manpower development are

indispensable for improving productivity and organisational performance in public sector emergency services. While the findings from the Nasarawa State Fire Service mirror global perspectives on the importance of human capital investment, they also reveal unique local challenges such as chronic underfunding, manpower shortages, and limited infrastructure. Addressing these issues will require deliberate policy reforms, stronger institutional frameworks, and the integration of modern training technologies to build a resilient and efficient emergency response system.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study set out to examine the impact of training and manpower development on productivity in the Nasarawa State Fire Service, with a focus on assessing how training influences employee productivity, determining the contribution of manpower development to organisational performance, identifying the long-term effects of training, examining challenges, and recommending strategies for improvement. The findings revealed that training significantly enhanced employee productivity, improved task efficiency, and strengthened emergency response capacity. Manpower development was also found to contribute to organisational effectiveness by fostering teamwork, efficiency, and overall service delivery. These findings are consistent with prior studies in Nigeria and globally, which highlight the positive relationship between human capital

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investment and organisational performance (Armstrong, 2006; Nassazi, 2013).

In terms of long-term effects, the study established that training raised employee morale and enthusiasm (93%), reduced workplace hazards (86%), and sustained quality service delivery (81%). These outcomes reinforce Human Capital Theory (Becker, 1975), which posits that investments in people through education and training yield significant long-term benefits for both individuals and institutions. However, the study also identified persistent challenges confronting manpower development in the Fire Service, notably poor funding, inadequate manpower, and lack of training facilities. These challenges align with previous research that documents systemic weaknesses in Nigeria's public sector organisations (Ewuim & Ubochi, 2007; Adele & Ibietan, 2017). Despite these constraints, the results confirmed a strong positive relationship between training, manpower development, and productivity, underscoring the importance of institutionalising structured capacity-building efforts in public service organisations.

Practical Recommendations

Based on these findings, the study recommends the following practical measures:

1. Institutionalisation of Structured Training Policies – Training and manpower development should be formalised through clear policies that mandate regular capacity-building programmes

for all Fire Service personnel. This would ensure consistency, accountability, and alignment with global best practices.

2. Increased Government Funding – Adequate financial allocations must be made to support continuous training, provision of modern firefighting equipment, and the establishment of specialised training facilities. Sustained funding will enhance both short-term and long-term productivity outcomes.

3. Recruitment of Additional Personnel – The government should address manpower shortages by recruiting more staff. This would reduce workload pressures on existing employees and enable broader participation in training programmes.

4. Provision of Modern Training Facilities and Equipment – Updated infrastructure, simulation tools, and advanced training equipment should be provided to ensure that personnel are exposed to practical, hands-on learning that prepares them for complex emergency situations.

5. Partnerships with Fire Academies and Training Institutes – Collaborations with local and international training bodies should be pursued to expose personnel to new firefighting methods, safety standards, and innovative technologies.

6. Integration of Digital Training Platforms – E-learning, virtual simulations, and digital training platforms should be adopted to

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complement traditional methods, expand accessibility, and reduce costs.

7. Policy Reforms and Monitoring Mechanisms – The government should adopt reforms that prioritise manpower development as a key performance indicator in emergency service management. Monitoring systems should also be introduced to ensure transparency and efficiency in the utilisation of training resources.

In sum, this study demonstrates that training and manpower development are indispensable to strengthening employee productivity, organisational performance, and long-term service delivery in the Nasarawa State Fire Service. Addressing the identified challenges through deliberate reforms, increased funding, and adoption of modern training approaches will not only improve staff efficiency but also ensure that the Fire Service fulfils its core mandate of safeguarding lives and property in Nasarawa State.

Contributions to Knowledge

The study contributes to the body of knowledge by providing empirical evidence on the relationship between training, manpower development, and productivity in the Nasarawa State Fire Service, a sector that has received limited scholarly attention in Nigeria. By employing both quantitative and qualitative methods, the research offers a holistic understanding of how structured training improves employee productivity, morale, hazard reduction, and

service delivery, thereby filling a gap in public sector human capital development literature (Olaniyan & Ojo, 2008; Adele & Ibietan, 2017).

Additionally, the study highlights the specific challenges—such as poor funding, inadequate manpower, and lack of facilities—that constrain training effectiveness in state-level emergency services. This provides valuable contextual insights that enrich comparative debates on the effectiveness of manpower development frameworks in public institutions across developing economies. The findings also reinforce Human Capital Theory by demonstrating how systematic investment in training yields long-term organisational benefits, thereby offering theoretical validation within the Nigerian public service context.

Suggestions for Further Research

Future research should expand beyond the Nasarawa State Fire Service to include comparative analyses across multiple states in Nigeria, particularly in fire services and other emergency response organisations, to better understand regional variations in training practices and productivity outcomes (Nwachukwu, 2006). Cross-country studies within sub-Saharan Africa could also provide broader insights into how manpower development challenges manifest under different institutional and policy frameworks.

Longitudinal studies are recommended to track the long-term impact of continuous training on

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employee retention, occupational safety, and service efficiency, especially in the context of changing technologies and growing urbanisation (Mathis & Jackson, 2004). Furthermore, future studies could investigate the cost–benefit trade-offs of integrating modern digital training tools, such as virtual simulations and e-learning platforms, into public sector emergency services. This would generate practical insights into how resource-constrained governments can effectively adopt innovative training strategies to strengthen institutional capacity and public safety.

References

Adele, A. & Ibietan, J. (2017). Public sector human resource development and service delivery in Nigeria: Issues and prospects. *Covenant University Journal of Politics and International Affairs*, 5(1), 72–86.

Adeniji, A. (2015). *Human resource management: Theory and practice*. Lagos: Pumark Nigeria Limited.

Armstrong, M. (2006). *A handbook of human resource management practice* (10th ed.). London: Kogan Page.

Becker, G. S. (1975). *Human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis, with special reference to education* (2nd ed.). New York: Columbia University Press.

Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2021). *Thematic analysis: A practical guide*. London: Sage.

Bryman, A. (2016). *Social research methods* (5th ed.). Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Cole, G. A. (1997). *Personnel management: Theory and practice* (4th ed.). London: Letts Educational.

Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Eme, O. I. (2015). Training and re-training of security personnel: A panacea for professionalization of Nigeria's security agencies. *African Journal of Political Science and International Relations*, 9(5), 192–199.

Eneanya, A. N. (2009). *Principles and practice of public personnel administration in Nigeria*. Lagos: Concept Publications.

Ewuim, N. & Ubochi, I. (2007). Training and retraining: A requisite for enhancing worker productivity in the Nigerian public service. *International Journal of Governance and Development*, 3(1), 45–56.

Esther Kingsley Edeh

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- George, D., & Mallery, P. (2019). IBM SPSS statistics 26 step by step: A simple guide and reference. New York: Routledge.
- Kothari, C. R. (2014). Research methodology: Methods and techniques (2nd rev. ed.). New Delhi: New Age International Publishers.
- Mathis, R. L., & Jackson, J. H. (2004). Human resource management (10th ed.). Mason, OH: South-Western College Publishing.
- Nassazi, A. (2013). Effects of training on employee performance: Evidence from Uganda. University of Applied Sciences, International Business.
- Nwachukwu, C. C. (2006). Management: Theory and practice. Onitsha: Africana First Publishers.
- Okoh, A. O. (1998). Personnel and human resources management in Nigeria. Benin City: Amfitop Books.
- Okotoni, O., & Erero, J. (2005). Manpower training and development in the Nigerian public service. African Journal of Public Administration and Management, 16(1), 1–13.
- Olaniyan, D. A., & Okemakinde, T. (2008). Human capital theory: Implications for educational development. European Journal of Scientific Research, 24(2), 157–162.
- Olaniyan, D. A., & Ojo, L. B. (2008). Staff training and development: A vital tool for organisational effectiveness. European Journal of Scientific Research, 24(3), 326–331.
- Obisi, C. (2011). Employee training and development in Nigerian organisations: Some observations and agenda for research. Australian Journal of Business and Management Research, 1(9), 82–91.
- Schultz, T. W. (1961). Investment in human capital. The American Economic Review, 51(1), 1–17.
- Shuibin, B., Benjamin, A., & Naam, T. (2020). Training and manpower development in the Ghana National Fire Service. International Journal of Safety and Emergency Services, 4(2), 55–68.
- Taherdoost, H. (2016). Validity and reliability of the research instrument: How to test the validation of a questionnaire/survey in a research. International Journal of Academic Research in Management, 5(3), 28–36.

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Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/iijlpsa/index>

Tharenou, P., Saks, A. M., & Moore, C. (2007). A review and critique of research on training and organisational-level outcomes.

Human Resource Management Review, 17(3), 251–273.

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